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USE OF TECHNOLOGIES IN SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS

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The methodological foundations of science are the primary philosophical fundamentals that determine the direction and essence of understanding objective reality, general and specific methods of understanding it, scientific penetration into its essence and laws of development in order to have a purposeful, rational impact on the world. is a set of positions, principles, categories, concepts. with him (Likhachev B.T., 1998). It is necessary to define methodological positions as a basis for building the concept of inclusive education. It is important to highlight such a framework that combines constructive ideas for a forward-looking, innovative movement of pedagogical science and practice that meets the requirements of today and tomorrow. Here, it is important not to be limited to an eclectically selected set of rules that are most appropriate and appropriate for the implementation of inclusive education. It should be a definition of the foundations of the formation of a leading system that provides an understanding of the direction of action of the pedagogical science and practice depending on the child, the individual.

Today, educational practice has developed in such a way that, in most cases, it divides children into normal (successfully mastering the program) parts, for which the methods and tools of education and upbringing developed over the centuries are "appropriate" and "inappropriate" ways. for those who are hard to read. in the format of stereotyped pedagogical thinking, in the arsenal of applied methods. Inclusive processes in the education and upbringing of children are identified as problems of modern Russian society, the reasons preventing their implementation are identified, a comparative analysis of foreign and domestic experience is being conducted (Malofeev N.N., Nazarova N.M., Shipitsina L.M., Furyaeva T.V., etc.). The study of inclusive processes in local pedagogy is carried out both in the conditions of the processes of organizing education and training of disabled children (corrective pedagogy) and in the conditions of their socialization and rehabilitation. The researches are mainly empirical in nature and summarize the accumulated experience of reuniting children (Shmatko N.D., Saitkhanov A.F., Farrakhova A.Yu., Melnik Yu.V., Semago M.M., Semago N.Ya., Penin G. N., etc.).

In general, students of not only pedagogy-psychology, but also all other fields of study should join their team under the guidance of tutors and strive forward in every aspect based on competition. Today, many developed countries of the world are switching to digital education system, because it has a great advantage in terms of time, quality of education, transparency, funds and technology.

The word "tutor" comes from the Latin "Tutorem" - a teacher, a coach. In some cases, he acts as a link between the lecturer and the listener, that is, he acts as a consultant and teacher in the wide acquisition of knowledge given by the speaker.

The main task of the "Tutor" is to strengthen the relationship between the university and students in the effective organization of the educational and educational process, to help students adapt to the university life and educational process, to provide them with methodological, social and psychological support and to help students is to increase love for the

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chosen profession. At the same time, they regularly analyze and improve the quality of boys' and girls' lessons, ensure that they spend their leisure time meaningfully, and are constantly aware of their social situation.

In the modern conditions of the experience of social and educational inclusion, the question of searching for methodological, conceptual foundations and clear interpretation arises, where the processes of building inclusive education and the processes taking place within it are studied. Attempts to justify the problem in the literature are often limited to calls aimed at ensuring the real right of children with disabilities to complete education. It is quite clear that the conceptual completion of the integrated education model will occur gradually in accordance with the implementation of comprehensive systematic research in this area. It is clear that the formation of a new theory of education reflects the synthesis of theories, including philosophical, pedagogical, psychological, medical, and others. The results of knowledge and theoretical research play the role of a scientific benchmark in the practice of inclusive education, ensuring its optimal functioning.

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